

Structural, linear and nonlinear optical studies of 4-methoxybenzylammonium tetrachloridozincate crystal

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Abstract

A semiorganic nonlinear optical 4-methoxybenzylammonium tetrachloridozincate (4MBAT) crystal has been grown by slow evaporation solution growth technique. Single crystal X-ray diffraction (XRD) study was carried out to determine the lattice parameters of 4MBAT crystal. XRD result revealed that 4MBAT crystal belongs to monoclinic crystal system with non centrosymmetric space group $P2_1$. UV-Vis-NIR transmission spectrum was recorded to analyse the optical characteristics. The transmission spectrum exhibit a good optical transmittance up to 1100 nm with the UV absorption edge at 271 nm. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral studies established the molecular structure of 4MBAT crystal. The second harmonic generation (SHG) test was performed to know SHG efficiency of the 4MBAT crystal using Kurtz-Perry powder method. The nonlinear optical efficiency of 4MBAT is 1.8 times higher than the standard potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP).